

METHODOLOGY OF CHEMISTRY.

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Annotation: This article is about the fact that the methodology of teaching chemistry is a scientific and educational science, the methodology of teaching chemistry is closely related to the science of pedagogy and its educational function is based on the laws of pedagogy.

Keywords: Electrochemical, physiology, pedagogy, theoretical.

It is known that the subject "Methods of teaching chemistry" teaches methods and technologies for mastering the basics of chemistry. Along with the educational issues of teaching any subject, there are also educational issues that are important in the development of society. Positive forms of education can also be successfully instilled in the minds of students in the teaching of chemistry. In addition, the comprehensive development of students' knowledge in the process of teaching the basics of chemistry is the foundation of science.

According to the historical development of the subject "Methods of teaching chemistry" is a subject that teaches the methods of teaching chemistry in secondary schools. During the years of independence, extensive work has been done to reform education. The main theoretical issues of chemistry, formed during several years of teaching at the school, the development of natural chemical resources of the republic and their products, the contribution of oriental thinkers to the development of chemistry, preserving the content of elemental chemistry and organic chemistry. , supplemented textbooks for chemists were created by chemists. For this reason, there was a problem of creating a textbook "Methods of teaching IGmyo", which is unique for the teaching of chemistry in schools, academic lyceums and professional colleges with continuous stages of education.

That the methodology of teaching chemistry is a scientific and educational science. Its integral connection with other sciences In the implementation of important discoveries, the methodology of work is important in the rapid solution of the problem posed to science. Scientific research done in the right way has led to great discoveries by the scientist. For example, the invention of the spectral analysis method led to the discovery of many elements in nature. The development of electrochemical testing methods has made it possible to quickly solve important problems in science and industry. Accordingly, the rapid mastery of the basics of chemistry by students depends on the method of teaching. Methodist scholars have developed various methods to increase the effectiveness of lessons in science teaching. They are used in the process of teaching chemistry.

The subject "Methods of teaching chemistry" teaches to master the basics of chemistry. Unlike science, which provides ready-made knowledge, science also serves as a scientific science, because new teaching methods are created in the process of pedagogical work. Improving the methods of teaching and learning by applying advanced educational technologies in the teaching process is also a scientific and methodological work. Teaching methods develop as the teacher works. Therefore, learning from the teaching experience of your advanced teacher is one of the important factors in improving the teaching process. Each new teaching method created by scientists is put into pedagogical practice at different stages of education. Effective methods are applied to the teaching process Nowadays, the process of teaching chemistry is innovative

The methodology of teaching chemistry is closely related to pedagogy. Because its educational function is based on the laws of pedagogy. Its methodological basis is the idea of national independence.

The object of influence of the methodology of chemistry is students of all ages of different ages, with different levels of character and different interests. Chemistry lessons written for school should be based on the age characteristics and level of

knowledge of the students. Physiology and psychology study the age-related characteristics of students. Processes of teaching and educating students

In order to solve their problems, future science teachers need to be well versed in the sciences of youth physiology and psychology. Due to the introduction of modern technologies in the teaching of chemistry, there is a function of computer science, ie the acquisition of computer-assisted teaching methods. Similarly, every teacher is a pedagogue. mathematical results of experiments. must be fully aware of the basics of the mathematical sciences in order to know the issues of analysis.

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